

Maga Magazinović (1882-1968) was a Serbian woman with pioneering dance artistic and pedagogical achievements. Her little-known ego-document *Moj život* (My life), was written in the 1950s and first fully published just in 2000. Maga describes her childhood life in Užice, for another 45 years (1882-1927) - moving to Belgrade, there continues her education, work, socialist activism and finally travel abroad to study with the biggest names of the performing arts: Emile Jaques Delcroze, Isidora Duncan or Rudolf von Laban. She describes the circumstances of the opening of a modern dance school in Belgrade, before classical ballet became established there. In the meantime, she married the German Slavist Gerhard Gazeman. After the Balkan and world wars, the death of their son and the discovery of his treason, Magazinović gave birth to their daughter Rajna, but at the same time decided to part ways. After the Second World War, she was working until the end of her life teaching dance and writing about its theories.

Moj život is an example of the first-person narrative and Maga's strategies of presenting intimacy through memoirs and confession. I will use the model of Małgorzata Czermińska's autobiographical triangle to assess the spectrum of author-reader relations. In Maga's various ego-document attitudes and her balancing strategies of testimony and confession in the process of autobiographical presentation I see one of the reasons of the censorship process. The second one is her-story, the subject of this intimacy description.

So, The first Czermińska's autobiographical attitude is "testimony, appears most often in diaries devoted to events of historical significance and people whom the author met in his life and considered significant enough to be passed on to posterity." It is like an epic picture of the world.

The second attitude, a confession, is closer to lyric, because the subject of autobiographical considerations here is the author's intimate world [ME].

The challenge is the last autobiographical attitude, it is like a dialogue in a drama: "it shifts the burden of attention from the artifact to the artist's contact with the audience, it opens the field for playing and provoking".

Although Czermińska writes that "in the matter of a specific text, we can only talk about the domination of one pole over the other, but never about the exclusion of one of them", I will risk a statement that the pole of confession and testimony is more or less balanced. We can see it in how Magazinović writes about the world of experience, motivation and influencing on reality:

Until then, the Faculty of Law was an indisputably male domain of study. In our club [female students], it was thought that we would conquer that domain as well. I also decide to enroll in the Faculty of Law. There was a lot of "pull-pull" about it. (...) I still enroll despite the main opponents of the "female invasion"(...) After two semesters, D. Rokićeva enrolled in law school, and she was the first woman to graduate from that faculty. Since in 1904 I graduated from the Faculty of Philosophy, I also stopped attending the Faculty of Law. The goal of my enrollment was achieved: the Faculty of Law also opened its doors to female students (176);

Writes about relationships and passion:

For me, the main thing was the age difference. Then belonging to various nations. The difference in their way of life and ours. And finally, perhaps the most powerful obstacle: how will I divide between art and motherhood (...) I came home like Hamlet: "a tear in one eye, a smile in the other"! My mother was the old, kind and close one, but I was not the same one who went into the world, full of good wishes. I saw a lot, heard a lot, visited many places, met many people, experienced a lot of beauty. But there was some sadness hovering above all that. I leave a part of my soul wherever I experience something beautiful (282);

Writes about non-normativity in art:

I was with Nadezhda, during the break, in her dressing room [Maud Allan]. The dancer was wearing tiny, flesh-colored panties. She said that she was "polizeilich verboten aufzutreten" [forbidden to appear by the police] without panties under the costume. Her English body was ruddy and seemed in its slenderness quite harmless and supersexual, and she treated it that way too. Completely like a naked child. Only in the costume of Salome, in the sensual movements of the rush, could she appear feminine (216);

And writes how much attention she devotes to providing details of the programs of her dance groups' performances, schedule of activities or the course of concerts - these are at least two chapters ("Ritmika u Domske gimnazije i produkcija rada moje škole", "Konflikt sa Klaudijom Isačenko") and fragments in others chapters. *Moj život* is a testimony, but not of so called "great history". It is a testimony to this close reality, Maga testifies to her own fate, to the brave choices of an independent artist.

[after rejecting the candidate for foreign studies twice due to the connection of other candidates and despite the better qualifications of Magazinović:] "I will, Professor, still go to study in Germany on my own clothes and bread, and even without your competitions - and with that I end the uncomfortable situation of apologizing again (204).

My život is also a testimony to the history of the socialist movement, in which she consciously raised the issue of gender equality:

We further translated Klara Cetkin's discussion Students and Socialism. By Lily Brown The Women's Movement. And we studied and discussed John Stuart Mill: The Subjection of Women. Somehow, the propaganda arrival in Belgrade of the most prominent German feminist of the time, Kete Schirmacher, the Danish writer, also a supporter of women's rights, Karin Mihaelis, and even the English suffragist Lady Aberdeen (or Astor) (175) also falls in that period.

In turn, from the attitude of confession, we can read in these testimonies the desire to be honest with herself and the recipient. More than once the author uses self-referential comments - those about remembering, uncertainty about one's own memory: "~~married, if I remember correctly, to some officer, whose name I do not remember~~" (81); she also follows memory in his story: "~~Speaking of suits, let me describe the national costumes of that time~~" (82); explains why she writes about something: "I don't really remember the dates of those visits. I cite them in order to know the mood and understanding of gender relations in society at that time and the struggle of women at the beginning of the 20th century for equality with men" (175). We can find in these quotations both features of a testimony, thanks to which we get to know the world of the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries from the perspective of a Serbian artist, and at the same time reveal herself to the reader through honesty. Thanks to this, it introduces the reader to the sphere of intimacy writing, thus a closer author-reader relationship is established (despite the time distance). At the very beginning of her ego-document, she confessed:

It occurred to me today to describe my life. (...) I am still afraid of one thing in this undertaking. Will my memory be sufficiently accurate and vivid, and will I be able to present its flows with the greatest degree of desired honesty and humanly possible impartiality towards myself and others? (42-43).

With this research approach of the autobiographical triangle, I wanted to define the intentions of Magazinovic's autobiographical narrative. I will use it as part of cultural memory to capture its text from the censorship side.

According to Aleida Assmann memory theory, communicative memory is the basic unit of cultural memory. Communicative memory is characterized by the lack of a unified form of memories, which it gains post factum, i.e. after embedding in a story that stabilizes these memories - a memory medium. It is also limited in time: it functions as a living memory that "always fades away with the end of the third generation."

This kind of memory in the case of the discussed text *Moj život* is fundamental. Thanks for this communication memory, the testimony and confessions of the dancer were published in general and saved from the final censorship - oblivion. They were collected and rescued by Jelena Šantić, a ballerina and choreographer of the National Ballet of Serbia. She was helped by Marija Janković, Rajna Gazeman (daughter), Radmila Popović (daughter-in-law), Marijana Popović (granddaughter).

On the other hand, cultural memory extends its boundaries to a long duration in the community, and "gains shape only through subjective perception, evaluation and assimilation, supported by the media, cultural institutions and the education system". What is very important, it has an impact on building individual and collective identities. In the case of Magazinović, such circumstances conducive to the occurrence in cultural memory are only beginning to emerge due to the publication of the text of the memoirs, i.e. 32 years after the author's death, and a certain cultural activity related to this publication. What else Maga's memoirs need, it is to go through "social selection and canonization processes based on educational institutions." At the same time, attention should be paid to the concept of power, which influences cultural memory, creating a content-focused canon.

Now I will use the bibliography included in the *My život* edition - there are Magi's articles about Maga and her works as books and concert programs: [table on the slide]

MM texts published:

14 - 1902-1936

3 - 1959, 1965 (2)

1 - 1996

1 - 1997

Books, lectures and concerts:

82 - 1940

1 - 1951

choreographic setting: 1911-1935

Literature on MM:

136 - 1905-1940

0 - 1941-1973

6 - 1974-1987

16 - 1992-2000

This bibliography clearly shows how Maga's works disappeared from public space after the Second World War. Why? We will probably never get a certain answer, but we can look at the context in which *Moj život* was written and published, and then we can see some regularities.

1. First of all - Mag certainly wanted to publish the memoirs, as evidenced by two texts from 1965, which appeared in "Letopis Matice srpske", very important Serbian journal (January, February). These are memories Sećanja. Detinjstvo u Užicu and Sećanja. Školovanje u Beograd.

2. Secondly - patriarchal culture (arguments 3, 4, 5, intimacy writing, rebellion,

As I indicated in the quotations, which I have mentioned to emphasize the narrative of the testimony-confession, we can find in the text the openness for intimacy. Many of Maga's confessions indicate that society wasn't ready for it – such openness of a woman in relation to her private life, for the surprising independence that accompanied her with every decision she described, or even for a rare entrepreneurship.

Vera Obradović, an expert in Serbian koreodrama, assessed that the modern dance of Maga was provocative and subversive not only in the field of art, but also in the perspective of a patriarchal society

How the "seductive" modern game was viewed in Belgrade at that time is recorded by Zora Prica Krstić on the occasion of Maud Allan's guest appearance:quat quat "When the American Maud Allan, a dancer in the style of Genevieve Stebbins and Isadora Duncan, was the first to play a classical dance in Belgrade (1908), it was there is a whole fuss about it. First, she had to dance in front of the areopagus: the "chosen ones" - artists and journalists, and only then the police gave her permission to dance in front of the audience barefoot!"

I mentioned the situation of Maga with Maud Allan before, calling it non-normative art. This performance of the Allan was the turning point in Maga's professional career - then she decided to take up the dance, which she learned from another controversial dancer, Isidora Dunkun. It was about the way the dance was performed - freely, barefoot, in light clothes that sometimes reveal more of the body. A revolution for the patriarchal society, deeply rooted in the national songs culture, was Maga's elevation of female characters from these songs to the main roles, to reflect on their fate. [These include choreographies: Jelisavka 1926, Smrt Majke Jugovića 1927, Kosovka devojka 1935.] As the female author of inconvenient, controversial and disruptive ideas, there could be no place in the cultural canon, neither during the life in the "bourgeois" Yugoslavia, nor in the socialist one that was still marked by the patriarchy.

3. Third – problematic herstory

The time of writing and the beginning of the publication of memories was dominated by the narrative of the state - socialist Yugoslavia - that emerged after the Second World War and lived the legend of a heroic struggle with the old order. So, the story of the new historical policy had no place for a voice from the past (*Moj život*) - in addition feminine, feminist and presenting a different vision of socialism.

To analyze the gaps in the cultural memory of Magazinovic, it will be necessary to look at the - indirect - political connections. I think they can be combined with work for the "Politika" magazine. I have to remind – she was the first female journalist in Serbia and in Politika. The

journal represented, yes, the idea of unity of all southern Slavs, but in the Greater-Serbian form. From the former journalist of this magazine we learn that Maga Magazinović was "removed for some political reasons", but he doesn't give details. Although Magazinović doesn't directly describe her political involvement in autobiography, it is difficult not to notice its connections in the intellectual milieu, about which she already writes quite often. It is especially worth paying attention to the herstoric network. Her close ties with Delfa Ivanić may have been of particular importance for the silence in cultural memory. I pay attention to Ivanić because her *Uspomene*, as she herself emphasized and the author of the study of her memoirs, Jasmina Milanović - were censored in a very clear way through self-censorship motivated by the political situation:

Fearing that certain statements might be misinterpreted, single words or parts of sentences, and entire paragraphs, have been deliberately omitted. This is especially true of the time which Delfa Ivanić spent in a communist prison in 1944. All deleted fragments have been returned to their original places in square brackets (...). For the same reasons, the manuscript does not include events in the life of Delfa Ivanić after 1945 (...). For her life ended with the advent of the new communist regime and she did not want to or could not write about that period.

Moreover, Delfa's humanitarian work was banned and the assets of her humanitarian organization seized by the socialist authorities - the memory media of her activities were erased/deleted. Ivanić described in her memoirs a relationship with power and a close relationship with the royal court. She also mentions, among other things, the visit of Magi Magazinović and Ljuba Jovanović-Čupa, whom he met thanks to her, a politically strong engaged figure during the first Yugoslavia and quite controversial. So, on the basis of this quick comparison, it is possible to draw parallels between the ego-document Ivanić and Magazinović. **It is a certain class identification - related to the bourgeois culture in Serbia - and gender - at the level of the threat to power by the independent and emancipating work of women.**

It is worth noting that also *Moj život* does not cover the period of the Second World War, as well as the time after the war. During this time and after the war, Maga's publications are also limited to almost zero, no longer collaborating with "Politika", in which she had her feminist, emancipating voice. It is also worth noting that Maga worked directly for Queen Marija Karadžiordziewić, giving lessons to her children.

It was only in the 70s and 80s that the mentions of Maga in professional literature began to emerge, but compared to the editions of autobiographical texts by men, this is of little interest. A certain apogee of ignorance was a series of memoirs and autobiographies, published in the collection of the Belgrade publishing house Nolit in 1989. The collection consists of 24 volumes, 21 of which are devoted to male authors, and the remaining three are collections of fragments of 43 male authors and only three female authors. So clearly the male voice prevails. It was not until the 90s that the work of cultural memory recovered, and so we reach the year 2000, when the memories of the Serbian artist were compiled and published - after years of society's work and changes in power.

The autobiography of Maga Magazinović shows the figure of a woman emancipating other women, independent, driven by her own desires, courageous in making choices and achieving success in line with the discrimination she faced. The autobiographical narrative of sincere testimony and confession strongly distorted the image of a patriarchal and socialist society. The perspective of a woman's body that frees itself from censorship limitations and its unconventional expression of intimate emotions through her work and writing is perspective, which has been subjected to double censorship of moral and ideological perceptions when

literature - confession of women and testimony feminist art - that did not meet the conditions of the official narrative was censored. The point is that "Feminist art [is] about changing perceptions, raising awareness, and pushing for change. The memories were thus "lost" in the archives' storage memory, and only after changes in state systems, ie the power that distributes knowledge, and the transformations of society, emerging from the regime of patriarchal schemas regulating the canons, could these memories be processed. We are talking about systemic censorship, derived from the power-knowledge relationship, coupled with the woman's position in patriarchy and controlled by cultural memory. Maga Magazinović's ego-document had to wait with publication until the turn of the century and the breakup of Yugoslavia. To sum up - it was "censoring by forgetting" in cultural memory.